

INVESTIGATING INTERFACIAL THERMAL CONDUCTANCE OF GRAPHENE/EPOXY NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The functionalization of graphene on interfacial thermal conductance (ITC) of graphene/epoxy nanocomposites was investigated using non-equilibrium molecular dynamics (NEMD) simulation. Moreover, the ITC for a single graphene and a few-layer graphene embedded within epoxy matrix were also examined. The influences of the surface modifications on the ITC were elaborated using the vibration density of state (VDOS) and the interaction energy. It was found that the graphene grafted with functional group demonstrates superior ITC than pristine graphene. The enhanced interaction energy between graphene and surrounding epoxy caused by the functionalization may be responsible for the improvement of ITC. In addition, the VDOS spectrums obtained from the functionalized graphene and epoxy matrix are more compatible and thus the functional group can effectively facilitate the energy transport with less phonon scattering in the interface. With regard to the few layer graphene, it was found that the ITC decreases when the layer number in few-layer graphene increases and eventually attains a certain value. Generally, increasing the number of graphene layer would increase the opportunity of the phonon scattering between each graphene layer as well as the outmost graphene layer and epoxy, which leads to the reduction of phonon transport intensity.

1 INTRODUCTION

With excellent thermal conductivity [1], graphene has been extensively utilized as an effective heat transfer media in polymeric nanocomposites [2]. Nevertheless, it was found that the thermal conductivity of nanocomposites was not dominated by the thermal conductivity of graphene itself but by the ITC between the graphene and matrix [3]. It is necessary to understand the mechanism of thermal transport at the interfaces if the thermal conductivity of nanocomposites has to be enhanced effectively. In this study, the influences of the surface functionalization as well as the few layer graphene on the ITC are of concern. The main concept of the functionalization is to minimize the interfacial phonon scattering and enhance the ITC. The underneath mechanism causing the improvement of ITC was then elaborated by considering the interaction energy and the VDOS spectrum between the graphene and surrounding polymer. On the other hand, the influence of few layer graphene was characterized by considering the VDOS spectrum of each graphene layer and the matrix as well as the interaction energy.

2 MODEL GENERATION

In order to investigate the ITC between graphene and epoxy using NEMD, the idealized atomistic structures for graphene nanocomposites was generated. Basically, two nanocomposites models was considered, one is the nanocomposites with a monolayer graphene as shown in Fig. 1(a) and the other is the nanocomposites with few layer graphene as show in Fig. 1(b). The graphene was placed in the middle section of the simulation box in which the epoxy molecular was properly loaded. Basically, the atomistic model contained 20 cross-linked epoxy chains each of which was composed of nine chains of diglycidyl ether of bisphenol F (DGEBF) and three chains of triethelenetetramine (TETA) polymer chains [4]. In addition, the graphene was simply constructed by carbon atoms arrayed in hexagonal pattern. The epoxy molecular was interacted with graphene through van der Waals interactions with the cutoff radius of 10\AA . It is noted that for the few layer graphene case, the monolayer graphene were arranged in A-B-A stacking sequence with the layer number ranging from one to eight and then embedded in the simulation box. On the other hand, for the functionalized graphene, three different functional groups, i.e. carboxyl group (COOH), amine group (NH_2), and hydroxyl group (OH) were grafted on the graphene layer as shown in Fig. 2. The functionalization ratio was 5% which was defined as the number of the functional groups divided by the number of carbon atoms of the pristine graphene.

Figure 1: Idealized atomistic graphene nanocomposites: (a) nanocomposites with monolayer graphene; (b) nanocomposites with five-layer graphene.

Figure 2: (a) a monolayer of graphene with 5% functional group; (b) carboxyl group (COOH); (c) amide group (NH_2); (d) hydroxyl group (OH).

The heat flow through the interface was produced by deploying heat source in the right hand side and heat sink in the left hand side of the simulation box as shown in Fig. 3. It is noted that the heat source and heat sink are all deployed on the epoxy and the same amount of energy supplied on the heat source would be removed from the heat sink. The ITC between the graphene and epoxy was then calculated from the temperature difference in the interface obtained from NEMD simulation. The NEMD simulations were conducted using LAMMPS [5] software and the interatomic behaviors were described using PCFF potential [6]. The simulation box with periodic boundary condition was equilibrated at 300K and 1 atm under NPT ensemble with a time step of 1 fs. Subsequently, the heating supply at $q=0.005\text{Kcal/mol}$. was implemented on the equilibrated atomistic epoxy/graphene model using NVE ensemble. When the steady state of heat flow was accomplished, the ITC between the graphene and epoxy was estimated from Fourier's law as

$$G = \frac{J_Q}{\Delta T} \quad (1)$$

where ΔT is the temperature difference between graphene and epoxy. J_Q is the heat flux and expressed as

$$J_Q = \frac{Q}{A} \quad (2)$$

Q is the energy added/removed per second in the simulation box. A is the cross-section area perpendicular to the heat flux.

Figure 3: Heat source and sink deployed in simulation box

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effect of surface functionalization

The ITCs of graphene/epoxy interface with three different functional groups as well as the pristine graphene are listed in Table 1. It can be seen that the graphene with surface modification exhibit superior ITC than the pristine graphene. Specifically, the graphene with NH_2 functional groups is the best among the cases and followed by the graphene with COOH functional group and OH functional group successively. In order to further characterize the role of the functional group on the ITC, the normalized interaction energy between the functionalized graphene and the epoxy was calculated as [7]

$$E_{int} = (E_{total} - E_{graphene} - E_{epoxy})/N_C \quad (3)$$

where E_{int} is the normalized interaction energy between graphene and epoxy, E_{total} is the total energy of the simulation box, $E_{graphene}$ is the potential energy of graphene, E_{epoxy} is the potential energy of epoxy. N_C is the carbon atom number within graphene. The calculated E_{int} for functionalized graphene epoxy nanocomposites are also listed in Table 1.

Functional group		OH	COOH	NH_2
Interfacial thermal conductance G ($\text{MW}/\text{m}^2\text{K}$)	103.55	120.68	130.48	136.48
Normalized interaction energy E_{int} (Kcal/mol)	1.348	1.569	1.686	1.779

Table 1: Effect of functional group on interfacial thermal conductance and normalized interaction energy

It is shown that when the normalized interaction increases, the corresponding ITC values increases. In addition, because NH_2 functional group can provide more hydrogen bonds with the neighboring epoxy [8], not only ITC but also normalized interaction energy are increased. The similar tendency was also exhibited by Lv et al. [9] who examined the interaction energy in the graphene/epoxy nanocomposite. Thus, the enhancement of the interaction energy can effectively improve the ITC of the graphene/epoxy nanocomposites.

In addition to the normalized interaction energy, the VDOS spectrum of graphene and epoxy matrix was investigated. This is because the ITC is relied on the efficiency of phonon transport in the interface and the reduction of the phonon scattering in the interface can improve the ITC. The extent of the phonon scattering in the interface is characterized by comparing the compatibility of the VDOS spectrums derived from graphene and epoxy respectively. The spectrum of VDOS is defined as

$$VDOS(\omega) = \int \Gamma(t) e^{i\omega t} dt \quad (4)$$

where $\Gamma(t)$ is the velocity autocorrelation function [10-11] and written as

$$\Gamma(t) = \langle v(t) \cdot v(0) \rangle \quad (5)$$

where $v(0)$ are the initial velocities, $v(t)$ are velocities at time t , $\langle \rangle$ indicates a statistical time average. To quantify the vibrational coupling in terms of VDOS spectrum between the graphene and epoxy, the degree of overlapping (DO) was defined using the Jaccard index as [12]

$$DO \equiv \frac{\int_{lb}^{ub} VDOS(\omega)_{Overlap} d\omega}{\int_{lb}^{ub} VDOS(\omega)_{Union} d\omega} \quad (6)$$

where ub and lb stands for the upper bound (150THz) and lower bound (0THz) of phonon frequency, $VDOS(\omega)_{Overlap}$ is the overlapped part between the two VDOS spectrums, and the $VDOS(\omega)_{Union}$ is the union of the two VDOS spectrums.

Figure 4: Degree of overlapping in the VDOS spectrum in graphene and epoxy: (a) pristine graphene (b) OH group (c) COOH group (d) NH₂ group.

The vibrational coupling between functionalized graphenes and the epoxy are shown in Fig. 4(a-d) with the values of DO. Basically, the values of DO from functionalized graphene are much higher than that from pristine graphene. Moreover, the NH₂ functionalized graphene also demonstrate the highest value of DO. Apparently, the functional groups on the graphene can efficiently enhance the vibrational coupling in the interface and the high degree of vibrational coupling obtained from NH₂ functional group significantly improve the ITC in the interface.

3.2 Few-layer graphene

In addition to the functionalized graphene, the layer number effect of pristine graphene on ITC was examined and explained in terms of normalized interaction energy E_{int} , and degree of overlap (DO). The ITC of graphene with different layer number and the corresponding E_{int} are shown in Table 2.

Layer number	Single layer	2 layers	3 layers	4 layers	5 layers	8 layers
G (MW/m ² K)	103.55	96.18	93.66	86.76	87.67	86.94
E_{int} (Kcal/mol)	-1.348	-0.759	-0.506	-0.379	-0.378	-0.376

Table 2: Effect of layer number on interfacial thermal conductance and normalized interaction energy

It can be seen that the monolayer graphene exhibit superior ITC than other few-layer graphene. Moreover, the ITC value decreases consistently until the graphene number up to three. When the graphene is more than four layers, the ITC value accomplishes a certain value which is no longer influenced by the graphene number. This is because the range of van der Waals interaction is only limited to the first two layers nearby the epoxy and more layer graphene would not cause any reduction on the ITC.

The VDOS spectrums of few-layer graphene and epoxy are shown in Figure 5. In addition, the overlapping area of the VDOS spectrums obtained from graphene and epoxy were also shown in the figures. It can be seen that increasing layer number does not remarkably change the shape and intensities of VDOS of graphene, but decline the overlapping area. The values of DO calculated using equation (6) are also listed in the figure. Apparently, increase the layer number in the few layer graphene would lessen the DO value such that more phonon scattering at the interface would be

induced resulting in lower phonon transmission probability [13]. As a result, the monolayer graphene demonstrating superior ITC with epoxy than few-layer graphene was suggested and employed in the fabrication of nanocomposites if the thermal conductivity of the nanocomposites needs to be properly enhanced.

Figure 5: VDOS spectrum of few-layer graphene nanocomposites: (a) monolayer (b) 2 layers (c) 3 layers (d) 4 layers (e) 5 layers (f) 8 layers.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The ITC of the graphene/epoxy nanocomposites was examined by NEMD. It was demonstrated with the improvement of the interaction energy and the vibrational coupling between the graphene and epoxy, the functionalized graphene can effectively enhance the ITC, which coincides with the experimental observations. More specifically, the graphene with NH₂ surfactant demonstrated superior ITC than those grafted with COOH and OH groups. The enhanced mechanism of the functionalized graphene was elaborated from the improved compatibility of the VDOS spectrums derived from the graphene and epoxy. In addition, increasing graphene layer number in the few layer graphene would decrease the ITC. This is due to the fact that low compatibility of VDOS spectrums was found in the few-layer graphene and epoxy system so that more phonon scattering occurs at the interface. As a result, in order to have graphene/epoxy nanocomposites with superior thermal conductivity, the monolayer graphene grafted with NH₂ surfactant is suggested in the fabrication of nanocomposites.

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